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* Tel/Fax: (024) 62 885 957 * Website: <http://truongvietjsc.com>
* Email: truongvietcp07@gmail.com

TẠP CHÍ HÓA HỌC & ỨNG DỤNG

HỘI NGHỊ HÓA HỌC HỮU CƠ TOÀN QUỐC LẦN THỨ X (20 - 22/09/2024)

TẠP CHÍ

HÓA HỌC & ỨNG DỤNG

JOURNAL OF CHEMISTRY AND APPLICATION / TẠP CHÍ CỦA HỘI HÓA HỌC VIỆT NAM - ISSN1859-4069

Số 3B(70B)/5-2024

SỐ ĐẶC BIỆT

HỘI NGHỊ HÓA HỌC HỮU CƠ TOÀN QUỐC LẦN THỨ X

(21 - 22/09/2024)

HỘI ĐỒNG BIÊN TẬP

NGÔ QUỐC ANH, NGUYỄN CƯỜNG,
TRẦN THÀNH HUẾ, CHÂU VĂN MINH,
ĐẶNG VŨ MINH, TRẦN TRUNG NINH,
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LÊ THANH HẢI

Tòa soạn:

164 đường Tựu Liệt
xã Tam Hiệp, huyện Thanh Trì, Hà Nội
ĐT: (024) 62885957 - 0983 602 553
Email: tapchihoahocvaungdung@gmail.com
Tài khoản: 002704060000831
Ngân hàng Quốc tế-VIB, số 5, Lê Thánh Tông, Hà Nội.

Giấy phép xuất bản:

Số 319/GP-BTTTT
Bộ Thông tin và Truyền thông
cấp ngày 14/6/2016

In tại Công ty TNHH in ấn Đa Sắc
13 Ngọc Mạch - Xuân Phương
quận Nam Từ Liêm - Hà Nội

* Tạp chí xuất bản hàng quý,
phát hành vào các tháng 3, 6, 9 và 12.

Giá: 200.000 đồng

Trong số này:

3B(71)/9-2024

3 Design and synthesis of some novel amino acid derivatives containing benzo[d]thiazole

Nguyen Duc Du , Nguyen Van Dat ,
Nguyen Thi Ngoc Mai , Ngo Lan Anh ,
Do Quynh Anh , Nguyen Thu Phuong ,
Bach Ngoc Lan , Pham Huu Dien , Duong Quoc Hoan

12 Flavonoids from *Combretum trifoliatum*

Nguyen Cong Thai Son , Le My Lam Thuyen ,
Pham Nguyen Kim Tuyen , Huynh Bui Linh Chi ,
Phan Nhat Minh , Nguyen Diep Xuan Ky , Bui Trong Dat ,
Huynh Thi Kim Chi , Mai Dinh Tri , Dang Van Son ,
Nguyen Kim Phi Phung , Nguyen Tan Phat

17 Glycosides from *Combretum trifoliatum*

Nguyen Cong Thai Son , Nguyen The Anh ,
Nguyen Long Nguyen , Thong Ngoc Lan Anh ,
Phan Nhat Minh , Nguyen Diep Xuan Ky ,
Bui Trong Dat , Huynh Thi Kim Chi , Mai Dinh Tri ,
Ngo Trong Nghia , Dang Van Son ,
Nguyen Kim Phi Phung , Nguyen Tan Phat

23 Release of lovastatin drug from poly(lactic acid) biomaterial

Nguyen Thi Bích Viet , Vu Quoc Manh , Tran Thi Kieu
Giang , Doan Thi Yen , Vu Thi Thuong , Ha Manh Hung ,
Nguyen Dang Dat , Vu Quoc Trung , Nguyen Ngoc Linh

31 Study on the effect of N/P ratio and cultivation conditions on biomass growth and phycocyanin production of cyanobacterium *Oscillatoria* sp. LBIOCTO

Dang Thi Mai , Bui Thi Thu Uyen ,
Ba Thi Duong , Nguyen Thi Phuong Dung ,
Luu Thi Thu Ha , Do Thi Cam Van ,
Nguyen Thi Thu Phuong , Tran Dang Thuan

42 Three 3-benzylphthalide compounds isolated from the moss *Erythrodontium julaceum* Paris

Nguyen Ngoc Khanh Van , Pham Nguyen Kim Tuyen

47 Copper-promoted directed amination of C-H bonds in benzamides to access 2-arylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones

Le Thi Vy Thanh , Nguyen Thi Thu Ha ,
Phan Thanh Son Nam , Nguyen Thanh Tung

52 Total phenolic and flavonoid contents, and antioxidant capacity of Vietnamese *Curcuma aromatica* Salisb

Bui Mai Hoa , Le Thi Minh Thuy , Le Thi Huyen

- 58 Molecular docking and pharmaceutical studies of chromenoimidazocarboline derivatives as VEGFR-2 Kinase Inhibitors**
Dao Thi Nhung, Le Tuan Anh
- 66 Microwave-assisted three-component synthesis of new pyranonaphthoquinone derivatives**
Nguyen Ha Thanh, Nguyen Tuan Anh, Le Nhat Thuy Giang, Nguyen Thi Quynh Giang, Nguyen Van Ha, Nguyen Thi Nga, Nguyen Thi Hien, Vu Duc Cuong, Dang Thi Tuyet Anh
- 72 Flavonoids from the aerial parts of *Oligoceras eberhardtii* Gagnep. and their cytotoxic evaluation**
Nguyen Thi Binh Yen, Trieu Quy Hung, Pham Van Cuong, Doan Thi Mai Huong, Nguyen Thuy Linh, Tran Van Hieu, Nguyen Manh Hung
- 79 Palladium catalyzed, quinoline-based directed arylation of C–H bonds**
Le Cong Hau, Tran The Danh, Phan Thanh Son Nam, Nguyen Thanh Tung
- 84 Study on the preparation of *Lycopodiella cernua* (L.) pic. capsules containing β -sitosterol and naringenin**
Thi Kim Tuyet Nguyen, Thi Thanh Mai Nguyen
- 89 Evaluating potential inhibitors of HEP-G2 from 14 new hydroxamate derivatives of lupane triterpenoids using molecular docking simulation and admet properties**
Dang Thi Tuyet Anh, Le Nhat Thuy Giang, Nguyen Ha Thanh, Dao Thi Nhung
- 95 Structure - surface adhesion relationships of *E. coli* fimh proteins and mannosides: A molecular analysis of the main regulators**
Nguyen Ha Thanh, Pham Viet Ha Quang, Nguyen Cam Linh, Pham The Hai
- 103 Preparation, characterization, and properties of some SiO₂ nanocomposite of polythiophenes containing hydrazone group**
Do Ba Dai, Nguyen Huu Thinh, Le Tien Dat, Le Thanh Nhan, Bui Phuong Thao, Dong Thi Thu Hang, Nguyen Ngoc Linh, Nguyen Thi Hong Nhung, Vu Quoc Manh, Vu Quoc Trung
- 109 Characterization of acrylic coatings containing poly(triethylammonium 3-thiopheneacetate) polyelectrolyte and nano-SiO₂**
Nguyen Thi Hong Nhung, Nguyen Kim Loan, Vu Quoc Trung, Bui Tuan Anh, Nguyen Ngoc Hai, Vu Viet Bac, Nguyen Ngoc Linh
- 116 Các hợp chất geranylphenylacetate glycoside và triterpenoid từ cây *Aphanamixis polystachya***
Ngô Anh Bằng, Phạm Hải Yến, Bùi Hữu Tài, Trương Thị Thu Hiền, Phan Văn Kiệt
- 123 Tổng hợp một số dẫn xuất mới từ madecassic acid có sự biến đổi cấu trúc vòng A**
Trần Văn Lộc, Nguyễn Thế Anh, Trần Văn Chiến, Trần Tuấn Anh, Trần Thị Phương Thảo
- 129 Tổng hợp một số hợp chất lai coumarin-pyrimidine, coumarin-benzothiazepine đi từ các hợp chất α , β -ketone không no**
Dương Ngọc Toàn, Đinh Thủy Vân, Khouamai Luethor
- 134 Các hợp chất phenolic và lignan từ loài *Symplocos cochinchinensis***
Lê Thị Giang, Ninh Khắc Bản, Hoàng Trọng Dân, Nguyễn Thị Thu Thủy, Vũ Mai Thảo, Nguyễn Thị Mỹ Ninh, Nguyễn Thị Ánh Tuyết, Nguyễn Xuân Nhiệm
- 139 Nghiên cứu ứng dụng medium chain triglycerides (MCTS) trong công thức son dưỡng nhân sâm**
Bạch Hải Nghi, Vũ Trung Đức, Đào Huy Toàn
- 149 Nghiên cứu sử dụng phản ứng đa thành phần để tổng hợp các hợp chất dị vòng mới khung dihydronaphthofuran có chứa nguyên tố flo**
Nguyễn Hà Thanh, Hoàng Thị Phương, Đặng Thị Tuyết Anh, Nguyễn Thị Quỳnh Giang, Trần Văn Kiệt, Vũ Ngọc Doãn, Nguyễn Thị Loan, Vũ Thị Thu Hà, Nguyễn Thị Kim Tuyết, Lê Nhật Thùy Giang
- 155 Nghiên cứu khả năng kháng oxy hóa và kháng vi sinh vật của cây cam thảo nam (*Scoparia dulcis* Linn)**
Nguyễn Thị Hoài Ngân, Văng Thị Kim Anh, Đỗ Thị Huỳnh Như, Tôn Nữ Liên Hương
- 160 Tổng hợp và hoạt tính gây độc tế bào ung thư của một số hợp chất từ zerumbone**
Phạm Thế Chính, Phạm Thị Thắm, Hoàng Thị Thanh, Vũ Thị Liên, Vũ Tuấn Kiên, Trần Thị Thu Phương, Phan Thanh Phương, Nguyễn Thị Thao
- 166 Halosit gắn dopo ứng dụng nâng cao khả năng chống cháy và cơ tính của hệ composit polyetylen**
Hắc Thị Nhung, Nguyễn Hồng Thắm, Nguyễn Linh Chi, Hồ Thị Oanh, Đoàn Tiến Đạt, Nguyễn Đức Tuyển, Trần Quang Hưng, Trần Quang Vinh, Nguyễn Văn Tuyển, Hoàng Mai Hà
- 173 Nghiên cứu phân lập và đánh giá hoạt tính chống oxy hoá của các flavonoid glycoside từ lá cây bình bát nước (*Annona glabra* L., annonaceae)**
Trần Thị Minh, Đỗ Minh Hiếu, Trần Thị Minh Trang, Dương Hoàng Thúc
- 178 Nghiên cứu bào chế kem chống nắng với dịch chiết vỏ thanh long ruột đỏ (*Hylocereus costaricensis*)**
Phạm Diệu Linh, Trần Thu Hương, Lê Thị Thùy
- 183 Hàm lượng, thành phần, hoạt tính kháng vi sinh vật kiểm định và kháng viêm của các lớp chất lipid trong loài rong nâu *Lobophora australis* Z.sun, Gurgel & H.kawai**
Đào Thị Kim Dung, Nguyễn Thị Nga, Đặng Thị Minh Tuyết, Trần Đình Thắng, Idania Rodeiro Guerra, Ivones Hernández Balmaseda, Đoàn Lan Phương
- 191 Chế tạo hệ hạt nano tổ hợp chứa astaxanthin và curcumin: cải thiện khả năng phân tán, nâng cao tính ổn định và tăng cường hoạt tính chống oxy hoá**
Hồ Thị Oanh, Hắc Thị Nhung, Đoàn Tiến Đạt, Quách Thị Quỳnh, Nguyễn Yến Thanh, Hoàng Mai Hà

- 197** Điều chế chất lỏng ion 1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octanum sol-gel làm xúc tác trong tổng hợp 4H-chromene
 Nguyễn Thái Thế, Nguyễn Tấn Lực, Nguyễn Thị Huyền Trân, Phan Ngọc Hồng Thủy, Trần Hoàng Phương
- 207** Nghiên cứu chế tạo điện cực dựa trên vật liệu khung hữu cơ kim loại CuBTC và FeBTC ứng dụng trong cảm biến điện hoá phát hiện đồng thời amoxicillin và enrofloxacin với độ nhạy và độ chọn lọc cao
 Đoàn Tiến Đạt, Phạm Thị Hải Yến, Nguyễn Thị Kim Ngân, Đoàn Tất Đạt, Trần Quang Hải, Hắc Thị Nhung, Hồ Thị Oanh, Nguyễn Đức Tuyển, Lê Quốc Hùng, Vũ Thị Thu Hà, Lê Thu Thảo, Hoàng Văn Hùng, Hoàng Mai Hà
- 213** Nghiên cứu tổng hợp hệ dẫn truyền thuốc plga-chitosan giúp cải thiện độ phân tán của diosmin
 Tôn Anh Khoa, Trần Thị Trà Mi, Huỳnh Thị Kim Chi, Nguyễn Hoàng Phúc, Nguyễn Thị Cẩm Thu, Nguyễn Thị Hồng An, Hoàng Thị Kim Dung
- 219** Một số thành phần hoá học và hoạt tính gây độc tế bào ung thư của hợp chất thiophene từ loài *Pluchea indica* ở Việt Nam
 Vũ Minh Trang, Trần Hoàng Anh, Phan Minh Giang, Đỗ Thị Việt Hương
- 223** Nghiên cứu chứng cất tinh dầu lá bạc hà (*Mentha arvensis*) thu hái ở tỉnh Quảng Nam và ứng dụng phối chế xà phòng
 Cao Văn Miên, Nguyễn Đình Bảo Trân, Nguyễn Thúy Hằng, Nguyễn Hồng Khánh Phương, Trần Thị Ngọc Bích, Đỗ Thị Thúy Vân
- 229** Nghiên cứu sơ bộ thành phần hóa học loài *Camellia phanii* Hakoda & Ninh
 Hoàng Thị Tuyết Lan, Nguyễn Việt Dũng, Vũ Thị Xuân, Bùi Thị Mai Anh, Nguyễn Thị Minh Hằng, Vũ Mai Thảo, Nguyễn Thị Mai
- 233** Các hợp chất triterpene glycoside khung (20S)-dammarane phân lập từ rễ cây Tam thất
 Hoàng Văn Hùng, Lục Quang Tấn
- 242** Các hợp chất cis-clerodane furanoditerpenoid từ cây dây ký ninh (*Tinospora crispa*)
 Nguyễn Văn Quốc, Bùi Hữu Tài, Phạm Hải Yến, Đan Thị Thuý Hằng, Lê Đức Giang, Phan Văn Kiệt
- 248** Các hợp chất flavonoid phân lập từ lá loài bùm bụp *Mallotus apelta*
 Nguyễn Hoàng Anh, Vũ Kim Thư, Phạm Thế Chính, Nguyễn Doanh Kiên, Nguyễn Xuân Nhiệm
- 253** Một số hợp chất terpenoid từ loài *Cryptolepis buchananii*
 Nguyễn Đức Duy, Ngô Anh Bằng, Phạm Hải Yến, Đỗ Thị Trang, Nguyễn Thị Kim Thúy, Nguyễn Thị Cúc, Nguyễn Xuân Nhiệm, Phan Văn Kiệt, Ninh Khắc Bản, Bùi Hữu Tài
- 260** Tác dụng kháng viêm của Aurantiamide Acetate từ *Gomphrena celosioides*: ức chế con đường tín hiệu Mapk trong tế bào Raw264.7
 Ngô Văn Quang, Đặng Vũ Lương, Hồ Đức Cường, Đỗ Thị Thanh Xuân, Thành Thị Thu Thủy
- 266** Các dẫn xuất của acid caffeoylquinic từ loài phi điệp biển (*Suaeda maritima* (L.) Dumort.) tại Việt Nam
 Bùi Thị Nha Trang, Bùi Hữu Tài, Đỗ Khánh Linh, Bùi Thị Mai Anh, Nguyễn Thị Mai
- 271** Ứng dụng phương pháp phân tích sắc ký lỏng khối phổ phân giải cao LC-HR-QTOF-MS định lượng quercetin và kaempferol có trong dược liệu Hoàng Cầm (*Scutellaria baicalensis* Georg)
 Nguyễn Thị Thúy Hằng, Trần Thị Yến, Nguyễn Thu Uyên, Đỗ Hoàng Giang, Ngô Quốc Anh
- 275** Khảo sát một số yếu tố ảnh hưởng đến quá trình ủ phân hữu cơ với tro bay từ nhà máy nhiệt điện đốt than chất lượng thấp
 Hoàng Thị Bích, Phạm Thị Hồng Minh, Trần Hữu Quang, Đỗ Tiến Lâm, Bùi Thị Thực, Hoàng Đại Tuấn, Phạm Cao Bách, Nguyễn Văn Trọng, Nguyễn Trọng Vinh, Nguyễn Trọng Vương, Trần Quốc Toàn
- 281** Nghiên cứu carboxymethyl kappa-carrageenan bao bọc lectin từ rong đỏ *Kappaphycus striatus*
 Hoàng Thị Trang Nguyễn, Lê Đình Hùng, Thành Thị Thu Thủy
- 288** Ba hợp chất flavonoid phân lập từ cỏ biển *Zostera marina* L.
 Hồ Xuân Thủy, Huỳnh Tiến Thịnh, Đoàn Lan Phương, Phạm Nguyễn Kim Tuyển, Lê Đức Giang, Trần Đình Thắng

DESIGN AND SYNTHESIS OF SOME NOVEL AMINO ACID DERIVATIVES CONTAINING BENZO[d]THIAZOLE

NGUYEN DUC DU¹, NGUYEN VAN DAT¹, NGUYEN THI NGOC MAI², NGO LAN ANH¹, DO QUYNH ANH¹, NGUYEN THU PHUONG¹, BACH NGOC LAN¹, PHAM HUU DIEN¹ AND DUONG QUOC HOAN^{1*}

1. Faculty of Chemistry, Hanoi National University of Education, Hanoi, Vietnam

2. Faculty of Science, Hong Duc University, Thanh Hoa, Vietnam

* Email: hoandq@hnue.edu.vn

SUMMARY:

Seven new amino acid derivatives containing benzo[d]thiazole (**5a**, **5b**, **5c**, **5d**, **5e**, **5f** and **5g**) were designed and synthesized successfully through a straightforward 5-steps route, achieving high yields of up to 96%. Structures of all samples were determined by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, HMBC, HSQC, and MS spectroscopic methods.

Keywords: Benzo[d]thiazole, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, amino acid, synthesis, HATU, coupling reagent.

I. INTRODUCTION

Amino acids are among the most crucial molecules in nature as they play a central role in forming protein molecules and act as intermediates in metabolic processes[1]. Combining bioactive heterocyclic molecules with amino acids has yielded significant results, making them promising drug candidates[2-3]. Drugs synthesized based on amino acids often exhibit low toxicity, high bioactivity and permeability, and favourable metabolic and pharmacokinetic properties, attracting the interest and research of many groups[4]. Specifically, compound **1** (an amino acid combined with a neocryptolepine-like scaffold), synthesized by K. Sidoryk *et al.* in 2014, showed

high activity against Gram-positive bacteria strains[5]; Suyoga Vardhan *et al.* synthesized compound **2** (an amino acid combined with 2,3-dichlorophenyl piperazine) in 2017, demonstrating excellent anticoagulant efficacy[6]; compound **3** (an amino acid combined with a quinazolinone scaffold), successfully synthesized by Rakesh *et al.* in 2015, exhibited notable antioxidant activity[7]; in 2019, Nezhawy *et al.* successfully synthesized compound **4** (an amino acid combined with a 1-oxophthalazine scaffold), which showed significant activity against MCF7 breast cancer cell lines[8].

Benzo[d]thiazole derivatives are polycyclic aromatic

Figure 1. Some examples of the combination of bioactive heterocyclic molecules with amino acids

compounds comprising phenyl and thiazole rings. This molecular scaffold is commonly found in marine organisms and various plant species[9]. Notably, this ring system has garnered significant interest and research from scientists due to its diverse and intriguing biological properties, such as anti-inflammatory[10]; antibacterial[11]; antiviral[12]; antioxidant[13]; and immunomodulatory effects[14]. As a result, numerous studies on the synthesis of benzo[d]thiazole have been published, specifically, the report by Linh et al. in 2017[15], and our group's reports in 2017 and 2018[16 - 17]. All these reports approached green synthesis methods, utilizing domestic microwave ovens, and resulted in the creation of many new benzo[d]thiazole derivatives.

Due to such intriguing benefits, the combination of

5

MABA MIC = 3.7 μ M

6

The most effective antioxidant at 62.5 and 125 μ g/mL concentrations with 32 and 38%

Figure 2. Some examples of the combination of benzo[d]thiazole with amino acids

II. METHODS AND EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials and Methods

Solvents and other chemicals purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Merck Corp, Aladdin, Vietnam, or other China companies were used as received unless indicated. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE 600MHz spectrometer in CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆ at 298 - 300°K. Chemical-shift data for each signal was reported in ppm units. IR spectra were recorded on the Mattson 4020 GALAXY Series FT-IR. Mass spectra were recorded on the Agilent LC-MSD-Trap-SL series 1100 spectrometer. Melting points were measured using a Gallenkamp melting point apparatus. A domestic oven, Sharp R-205VN-S, made in China in 2022, was used to conduct the reactions.

2.2. Synthetic procedure

General procedure 1:

A mixture of compound **3** (285mg, 1mmol), methyl ester of amino acids (1mmol), HATU (380mg, 1mmol), and NMM (330mg, 3mmol) was thoroughly mixed and added to a round-bottom flask containing 3ml of *N,N*-

dimethylformamide. The reaction mixture was stirred uniformly at 60°C for 3 hours. The progress of the reaction was monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) (*n*-hexane/ethyl acetate, 2/1). Upon completion of the reaction, the solvent mixture was evaporated to yield a yellow-orange solid. Subsequently, the solid was recrystallized in ethanol/water (1:1, v/v) to afford compounds **4a - 4g** as white solids.

General procedure 2:

A mixture of compound **4a - 4g** (5mmol) was added to a round-bottom flask containing 5ml of ethanol, followed by the addition of 10% NaOH solution (10ml), and heated to reflux for approximately 5 minutes. The resulting reaction mixture was neutralized with 10% HCl or 10% H₂SO₄ solution until pH = 4 - 5 was reached, forming a solid precipitate. Subsequently, the solid was filtered and washed with distilled water to obtain compounds **5a - 5g** as white solids.

(2-(4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)phenoxy)acetyl)glycine (**5a**)

Following procedure 2: To a mixture of compound **4a** (1.78g, 5mmol), ethanol (5ml) and 10% NaOH solution

(10ml) was heated to reflux for approximately 5 minutes. Recrystallization in ethanol/water (1:1, v/v) gave the product **5a** as a white solid (1.57g, 92%): mp. 398 - 300°C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 600MHz) δ (ppm): 8.46 (t, *J* = 6.0Hz, 1H), 8.11 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 1H), 8.05 (m, 2H), 8.02 (d, *J* = 8.4Hz, 1H), 7.53 (td, *J* = 1.2, 8.4Hz, 1H), 7.44 (td, *J* = 0.6, 7.8Hz, 1H), 7.17 (dd, *J* = 1.8, 7.2Hz, 2H), 4.67 (s, 2H), 3.84 (d, *J* = 6.0Hz, 2H). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 150MHz) δ (ppm): 170.9, 167.6, 166.9, 160.1, 153.6, 134.3, 128.8, 126.5, 126.2, 125.2, 122.5, 122.2, 115.6, 66.8, 40.5. ESI-MS, [M+H]⁺, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 342.9/100. [M-H]⁻, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 340.8/100.

(2-(4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)phenoxy)acetyl)-L-alanine (**5b**)

Following procedure 2: To a mixture of compound **4b** (1.85g, 5mmol), ethanol (5ml) and 10% NaOH solution (10ml) was heated to reflux for approximately 5 minutes. Recrystallization in ethanol/water (1:1, v/v) gave the product **5b** as a white solid (1.66g, 93%): mp. 306 - 308°C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 600MHz) δ (ppm): 12.66 (s, 1H), 8.41 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 1H), 8.11 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 1H), 8.04 (m, 2H), 8.01 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 1H), 7.52 (td, *J* = 1.2, 7.2Hz, 1H), 7.43 (td, *J* = 1.2, 8.4Hz, 1H), 7.15 (m, 2H), 4.65 (q, *J* = 14.4Hz, 2H), 4.32 (t, *J* = 7.2Hz, 1H), 1.34 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 150MHz) δ (ppm): 173.7, 167.0, 166.9, 160.2, 153.6, 134.2, 128.7, 126.5, 126.1, 125.1, 122.5, 122.2, 115.5, 66.7, 47.3, 17.1. ESI-MS, [M+H]⁺, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 357.2/100. [M-H]⁻, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 355.1/100.

(2-(4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)phenoxy)acetyl)-L-valine (**5c**)

Following procedure 2: To a mixture of compound **4c** (1.99g, 5mmol), ethanol (5ml) and 10% NaOH solution (10ml) was heated to reflux for approximately 5 minutes. Recrystallization in ethanol/water (1:1, v/v) gave the product **5c** as a white solid (1.73 g, 90%): mp. 310 - 312°C. IR (ν, cm⁻¹): 3298 (N-H), 1696, 1672 (C=O), 1602, 1543, 1522 (C=C, C=N). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 600MHz) δ (ppm): 8.21 (d, *J* = 8.4Hz, 1H), 8.11 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 1H), 8.03 (m, 3H), 7.53 (td, *J* = 1.2, 7.8Hz, 1H), 7.44 (td, *J* = 0.6, 7.8Hz, 1H), 7.13 (dt, *J* = 3.0, 9.0Hz, 2H), 4.74 (q, *J* = 15.0Hz, 2H), 4.23 (q, *J* = 6.0Hz, 1H), 2.13 (q, *J* = 6.6Hz, 1H), 0.92 (d, *J* = 1.8Hz, 3H), 0.90 (d, *J* = 2.4Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 150MHz) δ (ppm): 172.6, 167.4, 166.9, 160.3, 153.6, 134.2, 128.7, 126.5, 126.0, 125.1, 122.5, 122.2, 115.4, 66.5, 56.9, 29.8, 19.1, 17.9. ESI-MS, [M+H]⁺, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 385.0/100. [M-H]⁻, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 382.9/100.

(2-(4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)phenoxy)acetyl)-L-leucine (**5d**)

Following procedure 2: To a mixture of compound **4d** (2.06g, 5mmol), ethanol (5ml) and 10% NaOH solution (10ml) was heated to reflux for approximately 5 minutes. Recrystallization in ethanol/water (1:1, v/v) gave the product **5d** as a white solid (1.89g, 95%): mp. 320 - 322°C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 600MHz) δ (ppm): 8.20 (d, *J* = 9.0Hz, 1H), 8.09 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 1H), 8.02 (m, 3H), 7.52 (td, *J* = 1.2, 7.8Hz, 1H), 7.42 (td, *J* = 0.6, 7.8Hz, 1H), 7.12 (d, *J* = 8.4Hz, 2H), 4.72 (q, *J* = 14.4Hz, 2H), 4.26 (q, *J* = 6.0Hz, 1H), 1.85 (m, 1H), 1.43 (m, 1H), 1.19 (m, 1H), 0.88 (d, *J* = 7.2Hz, 3H), 0.84 (d, *J* = 7.2Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 150MHz) δ (ppm): 172.7, 167.3, 166.9, 160.3, 153.6, 134.3, 128.8, 126.5, 126.1, 125.2, 122.5, 122.2, 115.4, 66.6, 56.1, 36.3, 24.7, 15.6, 11.2. ESI-MS, [M+H]⁺, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 399.0/100. [M-H]⁻, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 396.9/100.

(2-(4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)phenoxy)acetyl)-L-alloisoleucine (**5e**)

Following procedure 2: To a mixture of compound **4e** (2.06g, 5mmol), ethanol (5ml) and 10% NaOH solution (10ml) was heated to reflux for approximately 5 minutes. Recrystallization in ethanol/water (1:1, v/v) gave the product **5e** as a white solid (1.91g, 96%): mp. 315 - 317°C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 600 MHz) δ (ppm): 8.38 (d, *J* = 8.4Hz, 1H), 8.10 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 1H), 8.02 (m, 3H), 7.52 (td, *J* = 1.2, 8.4Hz, 1H), 7.43 (td, *J* = 1.2, 7.8Hz, 1H), 7.14 (d, *J* = 9.0Hz, 2H), 4.66 (q, *J* = 14.4Hz, 2H), 4.31 (m, 1H), 1.59 (m, 3H), 0.88 (d, *J* = 6.0Hz, 3H), 0.83 (d, *J* = 6.6Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 150MHz) δ (ppm): 173.7, 167.3, 166.9, 160.3, 153.6, 134.3, 128.7, 126.5, 126.1, 125.2, 122.5, 122.2, 115.5, 66.7, 50.0, 24.3, 22.8, 21.2. ESI-MS, [M+H]⁺, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 399.0/100. [M-H]⁻, *m/z* (au)/relative intensity (%): 396.9/100.

(2-(4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)phenoxy)acetyl)-L-phenylalanine (**5f**)

Following procedure 2: To a mixture of compound **4f** (2.23g, 5mmol), ethanol (5ml) and 10% NaOH solution (10ml) was heated to reflux for approximately 5 minutes. Recrystallization in ethanol/water (1:1, v/v) gave the product **5f** as a white solid (2.00g, 93%): mp. 330 - 332°C. ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 600MHz) δ (ppm): 8.38 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 1H), 8.12 (d, *J* = 7.8Hz, 1H), 8.03 (d, *J* = 8.4Hz, 1H), 8.00 (d, *J* = 9.0Hz, 2H), 7.53 (td, *J* = 1.2, 8.4Hz, 1H), 7.44 (td, *J* = 0.6, 7.8Hz, 1H), 7.27 (t, *J* = 7.2Hz, 2H), 7.22 (m, 3H), 7.04 (d, *J* = 8.4Hz, 2H), 4.60 (s, 2H), 4.54 (m, 1H), 3.15 (dd, *J* = 4.8, 13.8Hz, 1H), 3.00 (dd, *J* = 9.6, 13.8Hz, 1H). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 150MHz) δ (ppm): 172.6, 167.2, 166.9, 160.1, 153.6,

137.5, 134.3, 129.1, 128.7, 128.2, 126.5, 126.4, 126.0, 125.1, 122.5, 122.2, 115.4, 66.6, 53.1, 36.4. ESI-MS, $[M+H]^+$, m/z (au)/relative intensity (%): 433.0/100. $[M-H]^-$, m/z (au)/relative intensity (%): 430.9/100.

(2-(4-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl)phenoxy)acetyl)-L-proline (5g)

Following procedure 2: To a mixture of compound **4g** (1.98g, 5mmol), ethanol (5ml) and 10% NaOH solution (10ml) was heated to reflux for approximately 5 minutes. Recrystallization in ethanol/water (1:1, v/v) gave the product **5g** as a white solid (1.70g, 89%); mp. 320 -

323°C. 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 600MHz) δ (ppm): 8.09 (d, $J = 7.8$ Hz, 1H), 8.00 (m, 3H), 7.52 (td, $J = 1.2, 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.42 (td, $J = 0.6, 7.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.08 (m, 2H), 4.91 (q, $J = 15.6$ Hz, 2H), 4.28 (dd, $J = 4.2, 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 3.61 (m, 2H), 2.17 (m, 1H), 1.95 (m, 2H), 1.87 (m, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (DMSO- d_6 , 150MHz) δ (ppm): 173.5, 173.2, 167.0, 165.9, 165.6, 160.6, 160.5, 153.7, 134.3, 128.7, 128.6, 126.5, 125.9, 125.8, 125.1, 122.5, 122.2, 115.5, 115.3, 66.3, 65.9, 58.7, 58.0, 46.3, 45.4, 30.9, 28.5, 24.5, 21.6. ESI-MS, $[M+H]^+$, m/z (au)/relative intensity (%): 382.9/100. $[M-H]^-$, m/z (au)/relative intensity (%): 380.8/100.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Synthesis

In the 2009 report, Huang *et al.* designed a molecular scaffold in which benzo[d]thiazole was combined with an amino acid via an isoxazole ring intermediate[18]. Subsequently, in 2020, Payaz *et al.* developed a molecular framework where benzo[d]thiazole was directly coupled with an amino acid through an amide group[19]. Taking a

different approach from the two reports by Abdel-Mohsen in 2019 and El-Meguid in 2021, a hydrazine-hydrazide derivative scaffold was designed, resulting in compounds with excellent anticancer activity[20-21]. In this report, based on the existing framework of Abdel-Mohsen and El-Meguid, our group designed the target compound framework **5a - 5g** by replacing the hydrazine-hydrazide scaffold with an amino acid scaffold, **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. Designing of target molecules **5a - 5g**

The retrosynthetic steps for synthesizing target compounds **5a - 5g** are depicted in **Scheme 1**. In the cleavage stage **I**, the transformation process of compound **3** to target compounds **5a - 5g** involves two steps. The first step is the coupling of acid **3** with the methyl ester of amino acids. In this study, HATU and a base *N*-methyl morpholine (NMM) were used as the coupling agent to facilitate the reaction, as this

method is relatively straightforward and yields esters **4a - 4g** with high purity and good efficiency, up to 90%[22]. Subsequently, esters **4a - 4g** were selectively hydrolyzed by NaOH in an EtOH/H₂O solvent. Due to the stability of CO-NH bonds in basic conditions, only the ester groups were hydrolyzed at this stage, resulting in acids **5a - 5g** with very high yields, up to 96%[23].

Scheme 1. The retrosynthetic pathway for the synthesis of target compounds **5a - 5g**

In the cleavage stage **II**, the transformation from compound **1** to carboxylic acid **3** also involves two steps. First, to form ester **2**, compound **1** is treated with ethyl chloroacetate in the presence of K₂CO₃ and NaI in DMF, yielding ester **2** with an 82% yield[24]. Subsequently, ester **2** is hydrolyzed by NaOH in an EtOH/H₂O solvent system to produce carboxylic acid **3**, producing an excellent yield of 97%. In cleavage stage **III**, compound **1** is synthesized from 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, as reported by our research

group, achieving an excellent yield of 98%[25]. After analyzing the retrosynthetic pathway of target molecules **5a - 5g**, a simple synthetic route for the amino acid derivatives containing benzo[*d*]thiazole from 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde has been designed, comprising 5 steps and utilizing readily available reagents, **Scheme 2**. The result is the successful synthesis of 7 amino acid derivatives **5a - 5g** with very high yields, with yields of 89 - 96%.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of compound **5a - 5g** from 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde

3.2. Structure determination

The MS spectrum data indicated that the structure of compound **5e** is consistent with the predicted structure. Specifically, the +MS and -MS spectra of compound

5e show molecular ion peaks at m/z 399.0 and 396.9, respectively, suggesting that the molecular formula of compound **5e** is $C_{21}H_{22}N_2O_4S$ with a molecular weight of 398g/mol, **Figure 5 (c)**.

Figure 4. 1H NMR spectrum of compound **5e**

In the 1H NMR spectrum of compound **5e** (**Figure 4**), a doublet at $\delta = 8.38$ ppm with $J = 8.4$ Hz is assigned to the -NH- group, and a doublet at $\delta = 8.10$ ppm with $J = 7.8$ Hz is attributed to H2 or H5. Similarly, a doublet at $\delta = 7.14$ ppm involving 2 protons with $J = 9.0$ Hz is assigned to H9, H13, or H10, H12, since H9 is equivalent to H13 and H10 is equivalent to H12. Two protons, H21 and H20, are assigned to doublets at $\delta = 0.88$ ppm with $J = 6.0$ Hz and $\delta = 0.83$ ppm with $J = 6.6$ Hz, respectively. Next, a multiplet at $\delta = 8.02$ ppm, corresponding to 3 protons, is predicted to include 1 proton from H2 or H5 and 2 protons

from H9, H13, or H10 and H12. The subsequent multiplet at $\delta = 4.31$ ppm is assigned to H16, and the final multiplet at $\delta = 1.59$ ppm is attributed to H18 and H19. Protons H3 and H4, each having two ortho interactions and one weak meta interaction, typically appear as triplet-doublets and can be assigned to signals at $\delta = 7.52$ ppm with $J = 1.2, 8.4$ Hz or $\delta = 7.43$ ppm with $J = 1.2, 7.8$ Hz. Finally, the quartet signal at $\delta = 4.66$ ppm with $J = 14.4$ Hz is assigned to H14. Unambiguously assigned signals will be clarified further using HMBC and HSQC spectra.

Table 1: NMR data of compound **5e** [δ (ppm), J (Hz)]

1H NMR	^{13}C NMR	HSQC	HMBC
-	C1	134.3	C1xH3,H4,H5
H2	C2	122.2	C2xH2,H4 H2xC2,C4,C6
H3	C3	125.2	C3xH3 H3xC1,C5
H4	C4	126.5	C4xH2 H4xC2,C6
H5	C5	122.5	C5xH3
-	C6	153.6	H5xC1,C3,C7
-	C7	166.9	C7xH5,H10,H12

^1H NMR		^{13}C NMR		HSQC	HMBC
-	-	C8	115.5	-	C8xH9,H10,H12,H13
H9	8.02, m	C9	126.1	-	C9xH10,H12 H9xC7,C8,C10,C11,C12
H10	7.14, d, 9.0	C10	128.7	-	C10xH9,H13 H10xC7,C8,C9,C11,C13
-	-	C11	160.3	-	C11xH9,H10,H12,H13
H12	7.14, d, 9.0	C12	128.7	-	C12xH9,H13 H12xC7,C8,C9,C11,C13
H13	8.02, m	C13	126.1	-	C13xH10,H12 H13xC7,C8,C10,C11,C12
H14	4.66, q, 14.4	C14	66.7	C14xH14	-
-	-	C15	167.3	-	C15xH14,H16
H16	4.31, m	C16	50.0	C16xH16	C16xH18,H19 H16C18,C19
-	-	C17	173.7	-	-
H18	1.59, m	C18	-	C18xH18	-
H19	1.59, m	C19	24.3	C19xH19	C19xH16,H20,H21 H19xC16,C18,C19,C20,C21
H20	0.83, d, 6.6	C20	21.2	C20xH20	C20xH18,H19,H20,H21 H20xC18,C20
H21	0.88, d, 6.0	C21	22.8	C21xH21	C21xH18,H19,H20,H21 H21xC18,C20

The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of compound **5e** revealed 19 signals corresponding to 21 carbon atoms. This includes 6 signals for 6 saturated carbon atoms and 13 signals for 15 aromatic carbon atoms. To accurately assign these carbon atoms along with the uncertain proton signals mentioned above, 2D HMBC and HSQC spectra were employed. Based on the cross-peaks in the HMBC and

HSQC spectra, all 19 signals in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum were precisely assigned. Additionally, the uncertain proton signals were fully assigned, including those of H2; H3; H4; H5, H9 and H13; H10 and H12 (**Figure 5 (a)** and **Figure 5 (b)**). The signals from the 1D ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR spectra, and the cross-peaks from the 2D HMBC and HSQC spectra are all presented in **Table 1**.

Figure 5. NMR analysis of compound **5e**: (a) a part of HMBC spectrum; (b) a part of HSQC spectrum; (c) a part of (+) MS and (-) MS spectrum

IV. CONCLUSION

Amino acid derivatives containing benzo[d]thiazole were successfully synthesized from 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde via a straightforward 5-steps process. The synthesis involved simple reactions, inexpensive and readily available catalysts and chemicals, producing 7 different benzo[d]thiazole-containing amino acid derivatives **5a** - **5g** with high yields ranging from 89% to 96%. The structures of the synthesized derivatives were accurately determined using modern spectroscopic methods, including ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, HMBC, HSQC and MS spectrometry.

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This research is supported by The Vietnam Ministry of Education and Training under the project code B2023-SPH-16.